

COMPETENCIES OF A MODERN LEADER: PROFESSIONAL AND PERSONAL QUALITIES.

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Abstract. This article highlights the activities of a leader: problems, approaches, methods, and techniques; it emphasizes the personal qualities a leader should possess. It also states that a leader's ability to increase the intellectual potential of their team is considered a high indicator of managerial skills.

Keywords: leader, activity, problem, approach, method, team, goal, action, interest, character, mind, feeling, will, freedom, quality, non-standard, state, appearance, interest, talent.

Today's processes of globalization and the rapidly developing competitive environment demand not only traditional management functions from modern leaders, but also systemic, innovative, and integrative approaches. Complex and changing conditions in modern organizations, the introduction of digital technologies, and new trends in human resource management are shaping new directions for improving leadership activities.

A modern leader is not only a person who manages the organization but also a leader who can inspire their team, adapt to changes, and focus on results. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Leaders should serve not only the state but primarily the individual and the family, ensuring their legitimate interests." The competencies of a modern leader are considered in two main areas:

Professional competencies are the knowledge, skills, and experience necessary for a leader to operate successfully in their field.

The main professional competencies include: Firstly, the ability to think strategically, set long-term goals and develop ways to achieve them; secondly, organizational management skills, effective management of resources (time, personnel, finances); thirdly, analytical and problem-based thinking, i.e., analyzing the causes and consequences of events and finding effective solutions to problems; fourthly, innovative thinking and openness to innovation, i.e., readiness to apply new technologies, processes, or ideas; fifthly, communicative competence is the ability to communicate clearly and effectively, exchange ideas with the team; sixthly, the ability to make decisions, i.e., make quick and accurate decisions, take responsibility; seventhly, financial literacy, budgeting, management of expenses and income, economic analysis; eighthly, legal and regulatory knowledge, i.e., understanding labor legislation, industry regulations, company policy.

Personal qualities reflect the leader's behavior, relationships with others, and personal values.

Important personal qualities include: firstly, responsibility, i.e., a sense of responsibility for decisions and actions; secondly, honesty, reliability, transparency, fairness, and trustworthiness; thirdly, empathy and emotional intelligence, i.e., understanding the feelings

of employees, creating a healthy psychological environment in the team; fourthly, stress resistance, i.e., maintaining balance in complex situations; fifthly, adaptability, i.e., the ability to adapt to rapidly changing conditions; sixthly, the ability to motivate and inspire, i.e., motivate the team towards a goal, dedicate energy; seventhly, effective time management, planning tasks according to priorities; and eighthly, the desire for continuous development and the pursuit of acquiring new knowledge and skills [2].

Considering the professional competencies and personal qualities of a modern manager, today's manager:

- knowledgeable;
- responsible;
- humane;
- strategic thinker;
- must be ready for continuous growth.

Only such leaders can lead their team to success.

Competence [3] is a set of knowledge, skills, experience, and personal qualities necessary for an individual to perform a certain task or work effectively and correctly. That is, it gives an idea of what a person can do and to what extent.

At a time when the country's economy is growing rapidly, leadership skills play an important role in ensuring free competition and the well-being of the population, and in the effective organization of management activities in organizations and enterprises. A leader must have a broad worldview and a system of thinking on issues of internal interaction in organizations and final interaction with the external environment. He must know how to take intelligent and conscious risks, possessing high universal human qualities and psychological abilities.

The ability to unlock the intellectual potential of one's team is the highest indicator of a leader's management skills. If a leader manages their activities through this, ultimately the effectiveness of the team's work will depend more on its employees than on the leader [4].

The dependence of the successful implementation of managerial activity on the age of the leader is based on research conducted in developed countries.

It was found that the average age of leaders of large manufacturing companies in Japan is 63.5 years, while the average age of American leaders in this category is 59 years[5]. One of the surprising aspects encountered when studying the leaders of large Japanese companies is their age. In some organizations (for example, Sony Corporation), the age of the company's president is limited to 65 years, but it is not surprising that many heads of firms in the automotive industry are 75 years old or older. In general, in Japan, the experience of a lifetime employee being hired at an enterprise is applied. It turned out that most senior managers have been working in their organization for more than 30 years. Research conducted in this area indicates that senior managers, if their health is satisfactory, are a great source of experience for this organization. When we talk about a leader's advanced age, we must consider not only their biological aspects but also their social aspects and life experience. Indeed, our people didn't say in vain that "What the elderly know, fairies don't know"[6]. However, the introduction of modern technologies into production requires certain skills in mastering them. Unfortunately, it's not difficult to find older managers who still can't learn how to work on a computer. In this regard, a young leader is often perceived as a factor that brings advanced technology and efficiency to the organization.

The average age of employees in an organization managed by a young leader is often low. Youth (around 30-35 years old) is characterized by a propensity for innovation and discovery, creativity, fearlessness, and adaptability to a changing environment. Unfortunately, in such an organization, older employees (over 40-45) are even viewed with suspicion. However, it has been established that a person becomes a master of their profession at the age of 35-55, masters knowledge in their field well, and feels a desire to implement inventions. At the same time, a calm analysis of the situation and a calm attitude are formed in them. Of course, it is difficult to say that all young leaders are supporters and inclined towards advanced technologies, but modernity is characteristic of young people. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of a young manager turning to modern and advanced production methods.

There is another psychological phenomenon that is no less important than understanding. This is reflection, that is, interaction and perception. One of its manifestations is understanding the thoughts of the interlocutor during the conversation or understanding the mood on their face. Reflection is characteristic of leaders, lawyers, teachers, commanders, orators, that is, all professionals engaged in communication activities. The ability to think creatively gives a leader a certain advantage over his colleagues [7.].

The method known as "brainstorming," that is, collective creative thinking, can bring great benefits.

The main thing in it is to achieve the set goal by randomly presenting the most unexpected, "unusual" ideas to the team's employees, stating and developing any plan that will help solve or approach the set task. This method allows you to have several options for solving the problem, some of which may even seem very strange at first.

Usually, a team of like-minded people can suggest hundreds of alternative solutions through 1.5-2 hours of research, and the leader has the opportunity to choose the most convenient one.

In our people, there is a saying: "Even if he is older, his heart is young." Therefore, a modern leader, regardless of age, should be a supporter of advanced technologies and capable of implementing modern production at the organizational level. This is a requirement of the times. Another important aspect: what should a leader's image be like? First of all, let's focus on the term image. Image (Eng. image - appearance, image) - a specific synthetic image that arises in people's consciousness in relation to a specific person, organization, or other social object, embodying information about the perceived object and encouraging social behavior. Creating the image of a modern leader is about his face, clothing, heart, sound thinking, culture of communication, mastery of the art of management, competence: such human qualities as knowledge, thinking, professional skills, intelligence, modesty, politeness, beauty, morality, morality, advice and example, raising the prestige of a person, increasing his reputation, gaining respect, relying on the traditions of teacher and student.

In other words, a true leader is the leader of this team, a person who seeks the benefit of their enterprise and organization and protects the company's reputation. No one is born a leader; only through selfless work and its effective results does a person demonstrate their leadership qualities. An important factor in the work of a managerial employee is the correct direction of the actions of various levels of the management apparatus in decision-making and its implementation.

"If a minister or khokim does not understand the essence and significance of the new law, does not show dedication in its implementation, it will be difficult to awaken initiative in people. If we ourselves, as leaders, cannot convince people of this, they will not follow us, and the implementation of reforms will be very difficult," said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

A modern leader is not only a manager, but also a team builder, inspirer, and leader. He thinks strategically, believes in people, and is ready for change. The success of such a leader depends on his personal qualities, his constant desire to learn, and his attitude towards people

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